

D4.5 - Verification of the final configuration of the system II

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1. Executive summary

This document reviews the whole system analysis reported in D4.4 and performed at the first stages of the RE-SKIN components development and integration into the toolkit. As such, the developments and elaborations carried out in the last 15 months are shortly reported and commented in terms of the single components criticalities and overall system integration issues to be accounted for and solved before installation in the Italian demo case.

In this respect, first the main technical information related to each component of the project are reported (Description of the technology), then design drivers and typical application and integration drivers into RE-SKIN's system are described. Subsequently, sizing/operation requirements and monitoring/control requirements are summarized. Finally, possible criticalities and barriers to the integration are identified and analysed.

At this stage (M15), while the single components development has not been finalised, some information on the undergoing laboratory tests is discussed. Finally, the calculation of the forecast energy saving due to RESKIN application is discussed.

2. Hybrid Building-Integrated Photovoltaic-Thermal (BIPVT) System

2.1. Description of the technology

The Building Integrated photovoltaics roofing system is a modern solution for sloped roofs that replaces traditional coverings with photovoltaic (PV) modules. These modules are housed in recycled aluminum profiles and generate solar electricity while maintaining the building's structural integrity. Airflow between the modules and insulation panels helps with cooling and increases efficiency. Additionally, box-shaped metal panels under the modules provide insulation and help with heat absorption. Briefly the key advantage of this system is not only renewable energy production but also the contribution to the building's thermal insulation and weatherproofing (Fig. 1). For the adaption of specific purpose of the RE-SKIN project, this system is designed to be installed practically on any type of sloped roofs proving its flexibility, while offering innovative performance rooted in established technologies.

Figure 1. General 3D View of the BIPVT Roof System

2.2. Design drivers and typical applications

Although BIPVT offers innovative performance, it is based on established technologies, adapted for the specific purpose as described below:

- 1) **Metal profiles:** made from recycled aluminum, provide support for connecting roofs with PV modules and also house electrical wiring for safety. Recent improvements include using a single-extruded piece for stability, accommodating thicker insulation panels, and enhancing thermal insulation. Snap covers are removed to reduce shadows on PV modules, and waterproof screws are used for sealing. Though less flexible, this design offers better stability and resistance, with widened upper parts, narrowed insulation housing, and horizontal side wings for secure installation. These profiles can accommodate different PV module sizes, it can be adjusted in width by spacing the supporting profiles as needed, and in length by sizing or joining the profiles according to requirements.

- 1) **Refurbished PV module:** in line with the project's circular economy approach, glass-tedlar laminates will be used, with mono- or polycrystalline cells, rear junction box and anodized aluminum perimeter frame. The typical size used for residential and commercial installations are respectively 165 x 100 cm and 195 x 100 cm. In all envisioned cases the BIPVT system can easily fit the modules. Even though, opting for smaller sizes may offer greater flexibility during rooftop installation.
- 2) **Thermal insulation panel:** constructed as sandwich panels with a biosourced polyurethane foam core encased in sustainable steel sheeting. These panels fit into grooves at the base of the profiles and are connected via tongue-and-groove joints, ensuring weathertightness with appropriate silicon. Recent manufacturing tests are conducted in the manufacturer's laboratory, validated mechanical, thermal, and fire resistance properties, demonstrating strong mechanical strength, excellent thermal performance, and acceptable fire resistance, although additional fire retardant may further enhance results.
- 3) **Completion modules:** to finalize the roof system, special blind panels are integrated into the aluminum profiles where PV modules are not installed. These panels, made from folded recycled metal sheets with insulating material cores, come in various sizes to fit seamlessly into the BIPVT roof.
- 4) **Supply and return channels:** a supply duct will be installed at the roof eaves, drawing in outside air through grilles, to ensure balanced ventilation in the BIPVT system. This duct will connect to parallel ducts beneath the photovoltaic modules, leading to a return duct near the roof ridge, which connects to the heat pump. Consideration is given to expelling unused hot air. Detailed studies on duct composition, sections, and connections will be conducted for RE-SKIN demo case studies, with various configurations explored.

2.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

By overlapping the existing roof and replacing the waterproofing and airtightness cladding, the BIPVT system integrates with the building envelope, enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability. This section will outline the setting in which the Building Integrated Photovoltaic-Thermal (BIPVT) system will be integrated as part of the RE-SKIN project. It will go into detail regarding the sizing of the BIPVT system, its operation, monitoring mechanisms, and other pertinent factors necessary to understand its overall functionality within the given project context.

2.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

The operation of the BIPVT requires ensuring proper ventilation beneath the PV modules to optimize thermal efficiency and electrical output. Additionally, the system should be integrated with a heat pump to utilize captured solar energy for heating purposes.

It is important to note that the technical information pertains specifically to sizing the system. Table 1 presents the main technical specifications required for sizing the BIPVT system, which will be analyzed and confirmed with the first prototype and monitoring/testing.

Table 1. Technical specifications, dimensions and features of BIPVT system

Technical specification	Range
Dimensions	
Size (Width/Height/Thickness) [cm]	90-120 / 100-165 / 21.3-25
Weight [kg/m ²]	25-30
Technical Features	
Sound attenuation in operating conditions [dBA]	≈ 30
Water penetration	Sealed
Air tightness	Class A
Reaction to fire (Class)	BS3D0
Thermal transmittance [W/m ² K]	0.6-0.3
Energy performance	
Electric Efficiency [%]	15-20
Electric Power Output in STC [Wp/m ²]	150-200
Maximum System Voltage [V]	≈ 1000
Solar Thermal Power [W/m ²]	150-200
Thermal Efficiency [%] (UNI 8937)	20-45

2.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

The dimensions, performance, and desired characteristics of this system will be thoroughly examined and validated through the initial prototype and testing/monitoring processes.

In the RE-SKIN project, the BIPVT system needs to be monitored and controlled effectively. The need to keep track of how much electricity and heat the system is producing, and the control mechanisms in place to manage the system's load, store excess energy, and distribute power efficiently.

2.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

The integration of BIPVT systems with the building envelope and other energy systems, along with the installation process, can present various challenges. Prior to installation, a thorough examination of the existing roof's condition is essential. The strength and bearing capacity of the roof must also be evaluated.

The PV panels are mounted, with the electrical cables connected accordingly, these steps must be carefully executed to ensure a successful integration of the BIPVT system within the project.

For the integration of BIPVT systems in buildings using TRNSYS simulation, several important factors require attention. Firstly, accurate modelling, representation, and connection of the BIPVT system within the software are crucial to ensure reliable simulation results. Secondly, obtaining precise input data is essential for realistic simulations. Additionally, architectural integration should consider aesthetics, structural compatibility, and should be precise and defined to get reliable results.

3. DC heat pump

3.1. Description of the technology

The proposed system is a Heat Pump (HP), a DC-powered refrigeration system (Fig. 2). It provides heating, cooling and DHW production. It consists of a compressor, condenser, evaporator, and expansion valve, operating on a standard vapor-compression cycle. The compressor converts the liquid refrigerant into a heated gas, which is then condensed in the condenser. This HP is an air-water ducted unit, installable indoors, exchanges heat with ambient air via air ducts to produce heated or chilled water efficiently.

Figure 2. Heat Pump principle and design

3.2. Design drivers and typical applications

The heat pump is a Monoblock air water heat pump, all the main components are placed in one unique block machine (the main body). This allows to save the installation space and improve acoustic and aesthetic aspects. The heat pump Monoblock is formed by following three parts:

- 1) **Main Body:** it can be divided into two parts, upper and lower. The upper parts of the heat pump include an air-cooled fin-and-tube heat exchanger and an axial fan, integrated with a duct system for ambient air intake. The heat pump is tightly coupled with the duct system, with an installation area of about 720×920 mm. Airflow is routed to the heat exchanger via support of axial fans, targeting a flow rate between $5000 - 8000$ m³/h. Frost accumulation on the heat exchanger surface due to weather conditions can be eliminated through periodic de-frosting and drainage via a condensate drain hose at the heat pump bottom. The lower part of the heat

pump includes the compressor and other components of the refrigeration cycle. Additionally, it contains a heat exchanger for the water flow cycle, with water inlet and outlet ports positioned at the bottom, along with electrical connection ports.

- 2) **Powerbox:** The main body does not include the control system, instead the power box consists of the main control board, remote control gateway and manual controller system.
- 3) **Hydrobox:** Comprising pumps for the heating/cooling circuit and domestic hot water, alongside a heating rod. It’s optional, depending on site requirements, with pump sizes varied according to each building's HVAC system design.

3.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

The heat pump is designed to be placed inside the building and take in ambient air from the outside, which allow for efficient heating and cooling functions. Using a DC power supply enhance the advantages of the HP, allowing a direct power from PV energy or stored batteries without requiring an additional inverter. The Integration of HP into RE-SKIN system offers both energy efficiency and flexibility in using renewable energy sources.

The heat pump is controlled by the network controller placed in the Powerbox which accepts user requests and control the heat pump system, by interfacing with the RE-SKIN energy management system. The heat pump includes remote control service to analyze and control the heat pumps from remote place when the heat pumps are connected to internet network.

3.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

For sizing and operational requirements, several key factors must be considered. Firstly, the duct installation area should have dimensions around 720 × 920 mm to ensure adequate space allocation. Axial fans facilitate airflow within the system, directing it to the heat exchanger. The version currently under development requires a minimum flow rate of 2000 m³/h for proper ventilation, while optimal performance is achieved within a recommended nominal range of 5000 – 8000 m³/h, enhancing heating and cooling efficiency. It is significant to consider the technical and performance specifications while sizing the heat pump system. Table 2 presents the key technical specifications and performance characteristics of the system.

Table 2. Technical specifications, dimensions and features of Heat Pump

Technical specification	Range
Dimensions	
Size (Width/Height/Thickness) [cm]	100-130/190-230/100-120
Weight [kg/m ²]	300-400
Technical Features	
Air volume [m ³ /h]	2000-8000

Air inlet flow temperature [°C]	15 – 45
Volume water flow [m ³ /h]	0.5 – 3.5
Heat pump water outlet temperature [°C]	20 - 60
Working fluid	R515B
Compressor	Scroll
Compressor speed [rpm]	1200 – 5000
Fill amount [Liter]	4 – 8
Oil amount [Liter]	1 – 3
Power supply type	DC
Input voltage [V]	600 – 700
Compressor input voltage [V]	400
Frequency [Hz]	50
Current [A]	15 – 25
Fuse-fan	thermal relay
Max. nominal current – fan [A]	1.1 – 1.7
Earth leakage circuit breaker [mA]	30
Fan power [W]	50 – 500
Energy performance	
Nominal heating capacity [kW]	12 – 18
Nominal cooling capacity [kW]	9 - 12
Compressor power consumption [kW]	2 – 10
COP (heating)	2.5 – 5.5
air source	-10 – 10°C
water target temperature	25 – 45°C
EER (cooling)	3.5 – 6
air source	35°C – 20°C
water target temperature	7 – 12°C
Main operation feature-air side	
Maximum air flow rate in heating mode [m ³ /h]	8000
Minimum air flow rate in heating mode [m ³ /h]	2000
Maximum air flow rate in cooling mode [m ³ /h]	8000
Minimum air flow rate in cooling mode [m ³ /h]	2000
Maximum air inlet temperature [°C]	45
Minimum air inlet temperature [°C]	-15
Maximum operating relative humidity (at max. temperature) [%]	90
Minimum operating relative humidity (at min. temperature) [%]	25
Main operation features water side	
Maximum output water flow rate [l/s]	1
Minimum output water flow rate [l/s]	0.56
Maximum water output temperature (heating) [°C]	60
Minimum water output temperature (heating) [°C]	15
Maximum water input temperature (heating) [°C]	55
Minimum water input temperature (heating) [°C]	10
Maximum water output temperature (cooling) [°C]	35

Minimum water output temperature (cooling) [°C]	10
Maximum water input temperature (cooling) [°C]	40
Minimum water input temperature (cooling) [°C]	5
Nominal input/output temperature drop [°C]	3
Maximum hydraulic system pressure [bar]	6

3.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

Monitoring and control requirements for a heat pump typically include the need to monitor different temperatures at different positions within the system. This is crucial for ensuring that the heat pump operates within the desired temperature ranges. The communication interface designed by CTIC allow the exchange of input/output parameters between the heat pump system and the RE-SKIN energy management system, enabling effective monitoring and control. Table 3 below outlines the specified input/output parameters for control and monitoring.

Table 3. Input/output parameters for monitoring and control of Heat Pump System

Parameter	Category	IN/OUT
Outdoor air temperature	Sensor	Output
Heat inlet temperature	Sensor	Output
Heat outlet temperature	Sensor	Output
Buffer storage temperature	Sensor	Output
Energy sources inlet temperature	Sensor	Output
Energy sources outlet temperature	Sensor	Output
Coefficient of performance	Sensor	Output
Heating circuit pump	Actuator	Input
Buffer charging pump	Actuator	Input
Compressor	Actuator	Input
Error	System Status	Output
Status of the 4-way valve - air	System Status	Output
Heating/Cooling switch	Actuator	Input
Operating hour in Cooling Mode	Sensor	Output
Operating hours in Heat. Mode	Sensor	Output
Calorimeter_Heating	Sensor	Output
Electric meter_Heating	Sensor	Output
Calorimeter_Cooling	Sensor	Output
Electric meter_Cooling	Sensor	Output
Electric meter_total	Sensor	Output
Electric meter_capacity	Sensor	Output
Calorimeter_total	Sensor	Output
Calorimeter_capacity	Output	Output

Operating mode	Actuator	Input
Heat. inlet Setpoint temperature - Active	Actuator	Input
Clear (error, reset)	Actuator	Input
Outdoor temperature - Active	System Status	Output
Buffer temperature value	Actuator	Input
Buffer temperature - Active	System Status	Output

3.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

Integration of heat pumps can face several criticalities and barriers. Heat pumps involve complex electrical connections and refrigerant cycles, both of which demand specialized expertise for safe and efficient operation. Engaging qualified professionals is crucial to ensure proper installation, maintenance, and service of heat pumps.

During installation, it is important to consider specific factors to guarantee optimal performance. Heat pumps should not be installed on an uneven floor as it can affect stability and proper functioning. Sufficient space around the heat pump must be provided to facilitate proper airflow and maintenance. Additionally, the selected installation site should not be in the corner of a building because it leads to limited airflow, reducing efficiency and potentially risking overheating. It also hinders easy access to maintenance, making examinations and repairs more challenging, and the maximum elevation should not exceed 1500 meters above sea level.

Another aspect to consider is the management of condensate water generated by heat pumps, particularly during defrost mode. Proper disposal of condensate is vital to prevent water damage or system malfunction.

The integration of the heat pump with the MIMO converter and the grid presents potential challenges regarding voltage compatibility and operation of auxiliary components. The MIMO converter supplies 600-700 V DC to the heat pump, while the auxiliaries operate at 230-400 V AC. This voltage mismatch can result in electrical compatibility issues, necessitating proper voltage conversion and coordination.

Lastly, heat pumps are complex systems comprising various components like compressors, heat exchangers, and expansion valves. Accurate modeling of these components in TRNSYS simulation software can be challenging and requires a detailed understanding of their operation and performance characteristics. Careful consideration and precise modeling are crucial to accurately simulate heat pump behavior and assess system performance.

4. Storage System

4.1. Description of the technology

The battery system is the electrical energy storage/buffer for the electrical appliances connected to the MIMO unit. Its purpose is storing electricity produced by PV system to operate mainly the DC heat pump and DC smart fan coils.

Figure 3. Battery pack

The battery pack is made of recycled battery cells (EV) and installed preferentially inside the building, or in other protected places outside of buildings. The battery enclosure for the first prototype will be chosen among commercial solutions; this is due to the long time to design and certify new products.

4.2. Design drivers and typical applications

The battery bank will be developed using recycled battery cells of the LEV40 type, taken from the Mitsubishi Outlander PHEV. These cells are manufactured by GS-Yuasa, a Japanese company. Each individual cell has a nominal voltage of 3.75 V. They are arranged in groups of eight cells connected in series, forming what is known as a "battery bank" with a nominal voltage of 30 V.

Multiple battery packs can be connected in parallel to ensure the unique storage requirement of each building. This allows to achieve the required capacity by combining the individual battery packs together.

4.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

The batteries and related electronics such as the Battery Management System (BMS) and controllers will be placed in the battery enclosure on the building site. For safety considerations, the battery enclosure will be airtight to allow the installation of a gas-based fire extinguisher and

transported in certified trays of 8 cells each demounted. Once the batteries are in site, these will be installed and connected with electrical and communication cables to MIMO.

The charging and discharging operations of the battery bank will be determined by the RE-SKIN smart control system and actuated through the MIMO via BMS. It should be noted that the open position allows the electrical isolation of the battery from the MIMO and the Building. Through this integration, the RE-SKIN system's energy flow from the battery may be managed effectively.

4.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

Considering that the batteries cells are a dangerous goods, they require a specific condition of operations to ensure the safety of the surrounding environment and to make attention to their technical specifications for sizing the enclosure placement. A list of the key technical specifications and performance attributes associated with each individual battery cell and the 160 cells battery pack is listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Technical specifications, dimensions and features of storage system

Technical specification	Range
Dimensions	
Length [mm]	171 (±0.5)
Width [mm]	32.5 (±0.5)
Height (over terminals) [mm]	111 (±1)
Weight [kg]	1.4
Technical Features	
Storage temperature (recommended) [°C]	-20 to +35
Charge temperature [°C]	-25 to +60
Discharge temperature [°C]	-25 to +60
Lifecycle	5500 cycles (with 80% of initial capacity)
Energy performance	
Nominal voltage [V]	3.75
Operating voltage range [V]	2.75 to 4.1
1-hr rate typical Capacity at 25°C [Ah]	40 Ah
Charge voltage limit at 25°C (continuous) [V]	4.1
Charge voltage limit at 25°C (60mSec) [V]	4.2
Charge termination threshold current [A]	<0.5
Maximum Charge Current (-25°C) [A]	8
Maximum Charge Current (-10°C) [A]	20
Maximum Charge Current (0°C) [A]	40
Maximum Charge Current (10-40°C) [A]	100
Maximum Charge Current (50°C) [A]	80
Maximum Charge Current (55°C) [A]	40
Maximum Charge Current (60°C) [A]	16

Maximum discharge continuous current [A]	240
160-cells battery pack Energy performance features	
Nominal voltage [V]	600
Operating voltage range [V]	440 to 656
Nominal capacity (new cells) [kWh]	0.11
Expected capacity at time of installation [kWh]	16.8
Electric Features	
Nominal voltage [V]	540
Minimum voltage [V]	518.4
Maximum voltage [V]	604.8
Max charge current [A]	100, software limited to 50
Max discharge current [A]	240, software limited to 50
Nominal capacity (new battery) [Ah]	40
Min nominal capacity (recycled batteries) [Ah]	28
Energy storage [kWh]	15.12
Max charging power [kW]	27
Mechanical Features	
Dimension (L x W x H) [mm]	1640 x 440 x 1550
Battery cell weight [kg/cell]	1.4
Battery bank weight [Kg]	12.5
Battery and enclosure total weight[kg]	1000
Enclosure Features	
Material	Steel
Protection	IP54
Protection paint	powder coating
Opening	two front doors opening symmetrically on the total length

4.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

Within the project framework, the battery system requires various monitoring and control measures. These include tracking battery voltage and temperature for performance evaluation and safety and monitoring battery current for effective energy management. Communication and integration with the MIMO board and RE-SKIN smart control system enable coordinated control and data exchange. Fault detection mechanisms and alarms should be in place to identify abnormalities. By implementing these requirements, the battery system can be efficiently managed and integrated within the project framework to achieve optimal energy storage.

4.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

Integrating the battery system within the project framework can face challenges such as when integrating the battery system with existing electrical systems or devices. Complexity may arise

during integration, requiring expertise in aligning electrical connections, configuring control interfaces. This integration also requires addressing critical safety concerns, particularly regarding fire risks related to the batteries. Safety measures including sealed enclosures, and fire suppression systems are crucial to protect occupants and property while efficiently using energy storage.

5. Smart fan coils

5.1. Description of the technology

The innovative smart fan-coil technology revolutionizes building temperature regulation by utilizing a DC compressor to precisely adjust water temperature sourced from a centralized heat pump, ensuring optimal heating or cooling efficiency tailored to each room's energy demands. Its environmentally conscious design, featuring enclosures made from sustainable steel sheets with biosourced insulation, reduces embodied energy, making it a sustainable and energy-efficient climate control solution for buildings. Figure 4 shows the different components of a smart fan-coil unit.

Figure 4. Smart fan-coil unit

5.2. Design drivers and typical applications

The smart fan-coil technology prioritizes energy efficiency, precise temperature control, and sustainability, driven by the development of a reverse-cycle water source heat pump system installed within dwellings, featuring a small size rotary DC compressor for versatile heating and cooling capabilities with a maximum thermal power output of 3.2 kW. Notable enhancements include improved energy performance through a different compressor and ventilating fan, along with simplified installation and maintenance processes facilitated by snap-in fittings, offering a modular design adaptable to various configurations.

5.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

The integration of smart fan-coils into the RE-SKIN system involves replacing radiators seamlessly, utilizing existing or new hydronic pipes, forming a reverse-cycle water source heat pump system capable of providing heating and cooling for rooms up to 40 m² with a thermal capacity of up to 3.2 kW, ensuring efficient temperature control and domestic hot water provision, while leveraging existing infrastructure or incorporating new piping solutions for optimal performance.

5.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

The primary technical characteristics and capabilities of the fan-coil unit are shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Technical Specifications of the Smart Fan Coil

Dimensions	Specifications
Size (Length x Width x Height) [mm]	750 x 200 x 700
Weight [kg]	30 - 40

The small-size 48 DC compressor integrates both the rotary compressor and tangential fan, each unit containing a hermetically sealed refrigeration circuit connected to a heat exchanger, with the main performance parameters outlined in Table 6.

Table 6. Technical Features of the Smart Fan Coil

Technical Features and Energy Performances	Specifications
Power supply voltage [V]	48 (72 as an option)
Power supply current [A]	5 - 7 (may change if 72 V will be adopted)
Maximum air flow rate [m ³ /h]	500
Compressor type	DC compressor, reciprocating
Maximum useful thermal power (heating mode) [kW]	1.4 - 3.2
(cooling mode)	1.2
COP (Coefficient of Performance)	4.5 (W15A20)
EER (Energy Efficiency Ratio)	7.2 (W15A26)
Maximum sound power in operating conditions [dBA]	≈ 35

5.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

Temperature control is essential for Smart fan coils, allowing precise adjustment to maintain optimal comfort and energy efficiency by monitoring and adjusting temperature output, thereby ensuring comfort for occupants while minimizing energy consumption and responding effectively to changing conditions.

5.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

When positioning the fan coil, ensuring a clearance of approximately 30 cm for servicing, eliminating obstacles for air circulation, and following proper procedures for disassembly and electrical connections are crucial for optimal functionality. Challenges such as compatibility with existing infrastructure and limited availability of Smart fan coil models in simulation libraries like TRNSYS require meticulous attention and may necessitate custom modeling, while effective integration into building energy systems demands alignment with HVAC systems, building envelopes, and control strategies, posing potential compatibility challenges.

6. Modular Multifunctional Façade Cladding

6.1. Description of the technology

The multifunctional prefabricated façade system utilizes a modular structure primarily composed of sandwich panels and a substructure, designed to enhance energy performance, and reduce environmental impact using recyclable materials and innovative features such as weatherproofing, biobased coatings, and thermal resistance capabilities, contributing to a more sustainable approach to insulation within the RE-SKIN project.

6.2. Design drivers and typical applications

The integrated vertical façade system comprises sandwich panels, a recycled aluminium mounting structure, and detachable finishing elements, featuring sustainable materials like green coat steel and bioPUR foam core. GAR's standardized technical details ensure easy installation and inspection, utilizing tongue-and-groove joints and rectification profiles to maintain watertightness and design flexibility while minimizing thermal bridges.

6.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

The system can be integrated seamlessly into vertical facades with an adaptive closed chamber installation system, featuring tongue-and-groove joints for secure connections, ensuring an effective and cohesive enhancement of vertical facades.

6.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

Tables 7-9 show the primary technical characteristics and capabilities of the modular multifunctional Façade Cladding.

Table 7. Dimensions of Façade system

Dimensions	Specifications
Length [cm]	up to 500
Width [cm]	100 - 115
Thickness [cm]	6, 8, 10
Weight [kg/m ²]	13.6, 14.4, 15.2

Table 8. Technical Features of Façade System

Technical Features	Specifications
Sound attenuation in operating conditions [dBA]	≈ 30
Water penetration	sealed

Air tightness	Class A
Reaction to fire (class)	BS3D0

Table 9. Energy Performances Specifications of Façade System

Energy Performances	Specifications
Thermal transmittance [W/m ² K]	<0.33 (thickness 60 mm)
Thermal transmittance [W/m ² K]	<0.30 (thickness 80 mm)
Thermal transmittance [W/m ² K]	<0.26 (thickness 100 mm)

6.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

The successful installation of the multifunctional façade system requires a thorough approach, including careful assessment of façade complexity and accessibility, dynamometer tests for structural integrity, and meticulous monitoring of bracket and profile fixation, as well as precise placement of finishing elements.

6.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

Implementing the multifunctional façade system in balconies requires establishing fixed dimensions, strategically placing openings for gas piping, and overcoming challenges related to façade complexity and accessibility. Affixing panels to the substructure and wall is a significant aspect of installation, while developing representative TRNSYS models demands meticulous attention to detail regarding thermal properties, insulation values, and material specifications to ensure accurate simulation outcomes.

7. Multi-input/multi-output converter

7.1. Description of the technology

The MIMO converter serves as a pivotal device integrating a range of energy sources including PV panels, batteries, and the grid to ensure efficient power delivery in both DC and AC forms while effectively managing power flow among different sources and loads. Its design prioritizes outstanding conversion efficiency, compactness, and autonomous operation. Consisting of power converters, it is tailored to manage power distribution among batteries, heat pumps, smart fan coils, PV panels, EV chargers, and the grid, with a primary objective of enhancing renewable energy utilization, facilitating building-level power management, and curbing fossil fuel consumption. The modular structure and adaptable power levels of MIMO render it highly suitable for a diverse array of building types and sizes, spanning from small-scale residential units to expansive tertiary buildings.

7.2. Design drivers and typical applications

Table 10 describes the technical specifications of each component of the MIMO system to allow its holistic integration.

Table 10. Design drivers and applications of MIMO

Design Drivers	Typical Applications
Grid-connected four-leg AC/DC converter	Integration with utility grid
Multiple accessible DC ports	Convenient connectivity
Easily accessible DC port operating at rated DC-bus voltage	Customizable battery voltage ratings
Customized DC/DC converter design for various battery voltage ratings	Accommodating different battery types
MIMO Main Unit with control card for communication with RE-SKIN energy management system and BMS	Control and communication hub
4-leg AC-DC inverter (15-20 kW) for grid integration	Power conversion for grid connectivity
Bidirectional 10 kW DC-DC converter for battery interface	Battery integration and management
MIMO Remote Units for interacting with building subsystems	Interaction with PV panels and smart fan-coils
Dedicated DC/DC units for each fan coil device	Individualized control and power conversion
Power optimizer accompanying each PV panel	Optimized power generation from PV panels

Single DC/DC unit serving multiple fan coils	Efficient operation and management of fan coils
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7.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

The proposed solution involves integration of various components, such as PV modules, batteries, a heat pump, smart fan coils, and an intelligent EV charger, within a converter system. Two potential solutions are being considered to meet the voltage requirements of smart fan coils: dedicated DC/DC converters for each fan coil or installation of DC/DC converters to supply specific building sections. A technical discussion with SOLAR is ongoing to determine the optimal solution, considering both building characteristics and proposed configurations. The MIMO main unit is slated for installation in a service room within the main building, while MIMO remote units for fan coils will be placed near each fan coil outside individual flats if multiple smaller DC-DC units are chosen. Additionally, the MIMO remote unit for PV panels will be mounted below the panels and attached to the aluminum support.

7.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

The technical specifications for system sizing within the RE-SKIN project are outlined in Tables 11-13.

Table 11. Dimensions and Sizing of MIMO

Dimensions	Measurements (Width x Height x Depth) [cm]
Main unit	60 x 60 x 40
Power optimizer	< 10 x 10 x 8
Fan coil DC/DC - 300 W	< 10 x 10 x 8
Fan coil DC/DC - 3 kW	< 25 x 25 x 24

Table 12. Technical Specifications of MIMO

Technical Features	Specifications
AC/DC Four-leg converter port power	≈ 15 - 20 kW
MIMO DC-bus voltage range	min. 600 V – max. 700 V
DC-DC battery converter power	≈ 10 kW
DC-DC battery converter voltage	HV (600 –700 V) – LV (360 – 420 or 460 – 580 V)
PV system power	≈ 10 kW (power optimizer 300 W – 600 W each)
DC-DC fan coil converter voltage	HV (600 –700 V) – LV (48 or 72 V)
Solution 1: DC-DC fan coil converter power	≈ 300 W (one per each fan-coil)
Solution 2: Three-to-five DC/DC converters with 2 - 3.5 kW power each	

Table 13. Energy Performances of MIMO

Energy Performances	Specifications
AC/DC Four-leg converter port efficiency	> 94%
DC-DC battery converter efficiency	> 93%
PV system efficiency	> 90%
DC-DC fan coil converter efficiency	Solutions Individual DC-DC fan coil converter efficiency: > 90% Concentrated DC/DC converters efficiency: > 92%

7.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

The MIMO system requires comprehensive monitoring and control, including real-time power tracking, component state monitoring, and seamless communication, to ensure efficient operation and effective management.

7.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

Integrating the MIMO system into a project necessitates careful consideration of compatibility, design, and simulation challenges, including addressing infrastructure compatibility, managing installation procedures efficiently, and overcoming potential barriers in TRNSYS simulation due to model availability.

8. EV charger

8.1. Description of the technology

The technology introduced by ENELX for the RE-SKIN project comprises two electric vehicle charging infrastructures: "JuiceBox (version A)" and "JuicePole (Version B)". These charging solutions are directly powered and managed by the MIMO system, ensuring efficient and reliable charging experiences. "JuiceBox" is designed as a wall-mounted AC charger, capable of charging one vehicle at a time with a power range of 3.7 kW to 22 kW. On the other hand, "JuicePole" is a free-standing charger capable of simultaneously charging two vehicles at up to 22 kW each. Both versions are being considered for integration into the RE-SKIN package, underlining the importance of a comprehensive technical assessment to ensure alignment with the specifications of the MIMO converter in subsequent project stages.

8.2. Design drivers and typical applications

JuiceBox and JuicePole, introduced under the RE-SKIN project, offer innovative AC charging solutions for electric vehicles. The solutions aim to provide efficient and convenient charging, meeting diverse EV owner needs and fostering wider electric vehicle adoption.

8.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

Ensuring proper installation of the JuiceBox and JuicePole, including mounting by a qualified electrician, positioning within the vehicle's charge port range, using appropriate overcurrent protection devices and power cables, and aligning the JuicePole correctly to prevent operational issues and ensure optimal functionality.

8.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

The technical specifications and performance details of the two models are shown in Table 14.

Table 14. Technical Specifications of EV Charger

	Dimensions		Technical Features			Energy Performances		
	Width/Height/Depth [mm]	Weight [kg]	Operative Temperature [°C]	Operative RH [%]	Max. Altitude [m]	Power [kW]	Current [A]	Voltage [V]
Version A	153/180/42	5-10	-40to +60	5 - 95	2000	3.7 - 22	32	230 (1- phase) or 400 (3- phase)

Version	353/1475/333	60	-25 to +50	5 - 95	2000	22	64	400 (3-phase)
B								

8.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

The EV charger within the RE-SKIN project framework requires real-time monitoring of charging parameters, a comprehensive fault detection system for issue reporting, and integration with energy management and smart grid systems to optimize charging with renewable energy and grid demand.

8.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

Successful implementation of integrating an EV charger component within the RE-SKIN project framework and simulation using TRNSYS may be hindered by criticalities and barriers, necessitating the resolution of issues related to technical compatibility, interoperability with existing infrastructure, and the development and validation of accurate models.

9. DSS/BEMS Platform

9.1. Description of the technology

Significant enhancements to the Decision Support System (DSS) are in process, including the development of new models addressing circularity in collaboration with ENELX and POLIMI. These models, integrating Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Cost (LCC) data, will provide valuable insights for building owners, greatly enhancing decision-making capabilities, and contributing to sustainable and efficient building management.

9.2. Design drivers and typical applications

The adoption of WEB 3.0 principles like Distributed Applications and Blockchain's Ledger aims to improve security, accountability, control, ownership, and collaboration of distributed data within the building in the RE-SKIN project, highlighting a strategic commitment to enhancing data management and decision-making capabilities.

9.3. Integration drivers into RE-SKIN system

Seamless integration and effective collaboration between the DSS and Building Energy Management System (BEMS) in the RE-SKIN project are contingent upon their mutual understanding of collected building data, necessitating standardized semantics and nomenclature across all layers of the digital twin and RE-SKIN platform modules to ensure consistent interpretation, facilitate interoperability, and enable cohesive analysis, thereby allowing for comprehensive insights and control over building operations.

9.3.1. Sizing and Operation requirements

The DSS and BEMS platform needs to be scalable for managing extensive data and user loads, maintaining stringent data security measures for sensitive information.

9.3.2. Monitoring and Control requirements

Performance monitoring optimizes system performance, availability monitoring guarantees uninterrupted service, and security monitoring identifies and addresses threats, including unauthorized access, to protect the platform's integrity.

9.4. Criticalities and barriers to the integration

Integrating a Decision Support System (DSS) or Building Energy Management System (BEMS) with a database platform may encounter compatibility issues with other systems, necessitating thorough

testing and possible custom development to ensure smooth communication. Additionally, the installation process may be prolonged, demanding careful planning and coordination to minimize disruptions to operations.

10. Integration of the subsystems in the toolkit: energy simulation

This section provides a description of the foreseen performance of RE-SKIN toolkit in the first demonstration building. The ultimate purpose is to harmonize the performance of each technology, leading to an energy efficient behaviour of the RE-SKIN energy concept and ensuring the thermal comfort of occupants.

10.1. Methodology

In order to provide a reliable estimation of the energy performance, a detailed energy model of the building before the installation of RE-SKIN toolkit has been performed. In such respect, the input parameter characterized by the most uncertainty, can be retrieved by the calibration process.

It consists of systematically adjusting the model to align its predictions with actual energy consumption data from the building.

The main steps of the method adopted are:

- Building survey and data collection: This step involves gathering detailed data on energy consumption, local climate conditions, and building characteristics such as construction materials, building envelope properties, and occupancy profiles;
- Building energy model: after that, a preliminary model in TRNSYS of the building coupled with the existing HVAC is created based on collected data and initial assumptions about input parameters;
- Model calibration: After that, the data obtained from the simulations are compared to the building's actual energy data. The discrepancy between the simulated and measured values is quantified using statistical indicators such as Mean Bias Error (MBE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE);
Further, iterative adjustments of some parameters (e.g., infiltration/ventilation) are made to the model parameters to reduce the discrepancy between the simulated and actual data;
- Validation: Once the model reaches an acceptable level of accuracy, it is implemented by the adoption of the RE-SKIN toolkit.

A flow chart of the adopted methodology has been reported in Figure 5, while the details of the different steps as well as the results, are described hereafter.

Figure 5. Adopted methodology for building energy simulations

10.1.1. Building survey and data collection

According to the survey reported in the D.8.1 (Energy audits and surveys I), the building energy consumption for year 2022 has been retrieved and used as baseline for the model calibration. Since the consumptions are based on the above-mentioned year, a specific meteorological dataset that represents the climate conditions for the reference location over year is created. These data are created through meteorological observations made from ARPA station (<https://www.arpalombardia.it/>) and include variables such as air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and direction, solar radiation, and other meteorological parameters.

10.1.2. Building energy model

As discussed before, the simulations were carried out with the TRNSYS 18 software, which adopt different “types” to represent the different building/systems components (Figure 6), as follows:

- Type56 (Building Model) calculates the heating energy needs for each zone of the building based on building characteristics, weather conditions, internal gains and infiltration/ventilation air flow. The calculation of thermal transfers to the ground is made based on Type77 and standard EN ISO 13370. The internal loads have been assumed to be equal to 4 W/m².
- Type751 (Boiler) generates hot water to meet the heating demand. It sends the heated water to Type1231 (Radiator), which then distributes the heat throughout the building’s thermal zones.

- Type1231 (Radiator) receives hot water from Type751 and transfers the thermal energy to the air in the thermal zones defined by Type56. The radiator's performance depends on the temperature of the incoming water and the heating load of each zone.

Figure 6. The different TRNSYS Types used in the case of the building before renovation

The 3D view of the building is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Building 3D Model

10.1.3. Model calibration

The calibration process has been developed according to ASHRAE standards. According to these standards, the acceptable tolerance threshold of the statistical indices, the monthly NMBE and

monthly CV(RMSE) should be less than +/-10% and 30%, respectively. The equations used are written as follows:

- Determination coefficient (R^2):
$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$
- Coefficient of variation of Root Mean Square Error
CV (RMSE):
$$RMSE = \frac{1}{\bar{y}} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})}{n - 1}$$
- Normalized Mean Bias Error (NMBE):
$$NMBE = \frac{1}{\bar{y}} \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})^2}{n - 1}}$$

Since the parameters characterized by the most uncertainty is air infiltration, within the process, the adjustment of air infiltration (from 0.1 to 1 ACH) to match measured data, ensuring that the simulated results accurately reflect real-world conditions, has been performed.

10.1.4. Validation

As shown in Figure 8, the simulated and measured building energy consumptions are in good agreement considering an infiltration rate of 0.9 V/h. In such condition, the NMBE is found to be around -0.03%, less than the threshold of $\pm 10\%$, whereas CV(RMSE) is 5.15%, less than 30% on monthly timestep. Furthermore, the regression coefficient is equal to 0.99 (Figure 9). The annual building energy consumption measured and simulated, by compensation effect, are very close, 281.65 and 281.74 kWh/m², respectively. Hence, the simulation model was calibrated and validated, allowing a more reliable analysis and informed decision-making to be undertaken in the design, operation and energy management of the building studied.

Figure 8. Monthly comparison between measured and simulated energy consumptions

Figure 9. Linear regression between measured and simulated energy consumptions

10.2. RE-SKIN energy performance

10.2.1. Building and Systems model

Since the model of the existing building can be considered calibrated, the same model has been used to forecast energy savings due to the application of RE-SKIN toolkit.

This system was modeled considering the following “types” (Fig. 10):

- Type568-1 (PVT System) provides both electricity and heated air. The electricity helps power the system, while the heated air will be used by the heat pump instead of the outside air (generally colder) in order to improve its efficiency.
- Type941 (Air-to-Water Heat Pump) generates the hot water needed for both domestic hot water (DHW) production and space conditioning. It sends this water to the Type158 (Storage Tank) one for DHW and another one for heating/cooling. If the temperature of the DHW storage tank is less than 48 °C, water circulates towards the latter. If not, the water circulates towards the storage tank which will supply the smart fan coils.
- Type158 (Storage Tank) stores hot water for domestic use and, when the temperature is suitable, supplies the fan coil (Type137) with water for space conditioning.
- Type114 (Pump) circulates water throughout the system, moving it between the heat pump (Type941) and storage tank (Type158).
- Type166 (Thermostat) controls the system based on zone temperature setpoints, regulating the operation of the fan coil (Type137) and the heat pump (Type941) to ensure comfortable indoor conditions.
- Type137 (Fan Coil) receives water at the required temperature from either the heat pump (Type941) or the storage tank (Type158) and uses it to condition the air in the building zones as calculated by Type56.

It is worth noting that the smart fan coil is modeled as a combination between the Type 941 (air to water hat pump) and the Type 137 (fan coil).

Figure 10. The different TRNSYS Types used in the case of the building after renovation

10.2.2. Results and discussions

The installation of RE-SKIN on the existing buildings, allowed a primary energy saving of about 76%, considering a primary energy factor of 2.41. However, it should be noted that RE-SKIN provides also the cooling services; thus the energy saving based on heating and DHW alone is about 80% (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Primary energy consumption before and after retrofit

The monthly electricity consumption of the different end-uses after RE-SKIN renovation is reported in the Figure 12.

Figure 12. Monthly electricity consumption after retrofit

Moreover, it should be noted that, a significant part of the HVAC electricity consumption is covered, on yearly basis, by the energy production from the refurbished PV panel installed on the BIPVT roof (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. Monthly electricity consumption and electricity production